

Formation constants of some bivalent transition metal complexes of *N*-(2-hydroxy-4-sulfonaphthylmethylidene)-4'-bromophenylamine

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Complexation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with Schiff base ligand *N*-(2-hydroxy-4-sulfonaphthylmethylidene)-4'-bromophenylamine has been investigated using potentiometric method. The study has been conducted in aqueous medium at 25, 35 and 45° and at $I = \sim 0.1 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3).

The present communication describes the potentiometric studies of complex formation by Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with the Schiff base ligand *N*-(2-hydroxy-4-sulfonaphthylmethylidene)-4'-bromophenylamine (*p-p'*-BSHNA). The study has been carried out in aqueous medium at 25, 35 and 45° using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique¹ as adopted by Irving and Rossotti². The ionic strength (I) has been maintained constant at $\sim 0.1 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3). The Schiff base *p-p'*-BSHNA was prepared according to the reported method³ and its purity was checked by the elemental analysis. The identity of the compound was also checked by comparing its IR spectrum with that of *N*-(2-hydroxy-naphthylmethylidene)-4'-bromophenylamine.

Results and Discussion

Owing to the very low concentration of the metal ion used, the formation of polynuclear complexes was considered to be unimportant. The metal curve showed departure from the ligand curve at pH much lower than the pH of hydrolysis of the metal ions^{4,5} and this suggests that the liberation proton is due to chelation alone. The values of metal-ligand and proton-ligand formation constants, calculated by following usual technique^{2,6}, are given in Table 1. It was observed that with increase in temperature both proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants decrease, sug-

gesting that lower temperature is favourable for complexation. The stability order, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} < \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, of metal complexes is in accordance with Irving and Williams order⁷.

The effect of substituent on the M-L stability constant values can be visualized by comparing the respective values with those of *N*-(2-hydroxy-4-sulfonaphthylmethylidene)phenylamine (*p*-SHNA) carried out under identical conditions⁸. The general structural formula of the ligand is presented in Fig. 1.

p-p'-BSHNA : X = 5,6-Benzo, Y = Br
p-SHNA : X = 5,6-Benzo, Y = H

Fig. 1

It is found that the values obtained in the case of *p*-SHNA for Co (5.2), Ni (5.65), Cu (7.0) and Zn (4.45) are lower than the respective values with the ligand *p-p'*-BSHNA (Table 1). The higher value in the case of *p-p'*-BSHNA may

Table 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of *p-p'*-BSHNA and its metal complexes in aqueous solution at different temperatures

Cation	25°		35°		45°		ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2			
H ⁺	10.00	5.25	9.50	5.00	8.75	4.80	–	–	–
Co ^{II}	6.75	–	6.00	–	5.50	–	9.27	31.71	75.30
Ni ^{II}	7.00	–	6.25	–	5.85	–	9.61	31.71	74.16
Cu ^{II}	8.75	–	8.00	–	7.30	–	12.01	31.71	66.09
Zn ^{II}	8.00	–	7.50	–	6.90	–	10.98	21.14	34.08

Note

be due to the presence of Br in the aromatic ring where it behaves more as electron-releasing group via stronger mesomeric effect rather than electron-withdrawing group through inductive effect⁹. Such effect may lead to an increase in the donor ability of nitrogen atom in *p-p'*-BSHNA relative to *p*-SHNA and hence the stability value of M-L complexes increases.

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